

Newton's First and Second Laws Leading to Different Spatial Probabilities One Being Quantum Mechanical? Part II

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In Part I we argued that directional motion should be associated with a different spatial probability densities. $dt(x) = dx/velocity(x)$, however, taken as proportional to a density in the literature (1) does not distinguish. We suggested that Newton's first law is equivalent to Fermat's least time principle which for reflection from a fixed mirror is equivalent to $d/dx (px) x = (px)$. $(px)x$, however, may be written as $-i \ln[\exp(i (px) x)]$ which has the form of constant multiplied by \ln probability in information theory. Thus we suggested in Part I that $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability density which distinguishes direction in motion. We also noted that $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ which is linked to the $dt(x)$ density for constant motion and that $\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \text{constant } \delta(p_1, p_2)$.

In this note we wish to examine in more detail the notion of x , t and wavelength. $\exp(ipx)$ depends on x and $p = m_0 dx/dt$ or $(p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2})$ with $v = dx/dt$. x and t are continuous variables linked to the idea of invariance in space for constant motion. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ on the other hand define built-in particle space and time intervals for a given p, E . Thus $\exp(ipx)$ defines constant motion in space without the notion of time (i.e. t and x are independent within a built-in ruler gradation proportional to $1/p$ (two humps-one positive one negative). This leads to a contradiction if the particle is tiny compared to $1/p$.

On the one hand the particle has smooth motion $v = x/t$, but on the other a "created" particle length unit must be defined suggesting a probability density over the length proportional to $1/p$. To allow for the two, one must assume a constant average motion over the length $1/p$ as measured by an external ruler and clock and at the same time abandon the notion of following the particle in x, t (infinite resolution) within the length proportional to $1/p$ even though its probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ is well defined at each x .

Thus the identity of the particle is defined by the probability $\exp(ipx)$ within $1/p$ regions even though a direct hit with another particle within this region involves p . Furthermore given that the spatial probability defines the particle it is not enough to state that for two particles one has p_1 and p_2 , the spatial probabilities must distinguish by being orthogonal i.e. having a 0 dot product: $\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x)$. We argue in the note that not only is particle identity described by $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, but also conservation of energy and momentum in various problems.

In Part I we suggested considering the product of $P(p, x)$ and $P(-p, x)$ in order to obtain a constant value linked to spatial variance throughout x even though $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are not spatially invariant. We first note that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are the time reversal of each other and then consider $\exp(ipx)$ AND $\exp(-ipx)$ together within a little region of the order of $1/p$. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$, but each moves with its own density profile $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. Thus constant density ignoring the direction of motion seems to be identical to the product of the time reversed density states.

Even though constant motion is only a translation when viewed on average, we suggest that directional motion must be linked with skewed density and be based on internal distances and clocks. This contradicts the idea of a smooth translation and leads to an unusual probability

description within \hbar/p wavelength units. The catch seems to be, however, that one needs to introduce two dimensions in order to demonstrate the skewness linked with directional motion.

By creating a spatial wavelength, the region within is one in which one may not follow the particle in x and t i.e. x and t are independent as in the classical action: $A = -Et + px$. dA/dx partial $= p$, but one cannot write this unless x and t are independent and only represent constant v on average i.e. x/t . Finally the wavelength and interval in time, which are physical, are directly linked to ensuring conservation of energy and momentum in the direction of an invariant variable. We argue this by consider a two dimensional reflection problem i.e. Fermat's principle.

The Notion of Spatial Probability Means One Cannot Follow the Particle in x,t - Only on Average

It seems heuristically that directional motion should involve a skewed spatial probability density as energy/mass is shifting from one position to another. The idea of a smooth translation seems idealistic. In the Newtonian picture, one may consider a particle, at x_1 , move to x_2 in a time t . This implies that measurement is possible and does not disturb the particle and external rulers and clocks are used with infinite resolution. Thus motion to the right is characterized by p and to the left by $-p$. The two momentum values are distinguished as different numbers, one motion is the time reverse of the other and everything is smooth.

Consider next that a particle is tiny compared to the number \hbar/p for some range of p numbers. In such a case, even if its mass density is shifting to the right or left, this occurs at a very tiny length scale which is not seen by a ruler with markings every \hbar/p . In such a case one might suggest abandoning the notion of skewed density as being noticeable and utilize the smooth x,t motion.

The problem with this scenario is that a constantly moving particle moves whether it is measured by external ruler and clock with infinite resolution or not. Thus we argue it should have its own built-in clock and ruler with certain gradations. These we suggest should depend on E and p . Thus the notion of a tiny particle changing its mass density is not the issue, rather the issue is the creation of time and distance scales through E and p . As argued in previous notes, a distance scale requires a change in density i.e. a probability hump to define a length portion. This contradicts the idea of smooth motion and the idea of following the particle at x at each t within the built in ruler gradation. Smooth motion, however, must still hold on average i.e. the hump density must somehow map into a constant (when the direction of motion is removed). Why is this the case? We suggest this must hold because the same x used to define the probability distribution within the particle's built-in ruler gradation describes its motion throughout space. In other words the particle must be consistent with its own time and ruler gradations, but at the same obey in an average sense constant motion in space measured with an external x,t with infinite resolution.

X,t Independence and Link With Classical Action

We note briefly that x and t independence is equivalent to writing the classical relativistic or nonrelativistic action ($-m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ or $.5mt vv$) with $v=x/t$ to obtain $A = -Et + px$ and then

argue that x and t are independent. They are independent within a hump region because one cannot follow the particle in time. In other words, $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$. Normally in the Newtonian picture one would not consider changing x holding t constant. It is only if they are independent that this makes sense. Overall, however, that is on average $v = x/t = \text{constant}$.

Why Is A Complex Form Required?

In the above section we argued that because a particle generates its own built-in clock or ruler with gradations which may depend on E and p . In order to have such gradations, one may no longer describe the particle's motion in time, although spatial "probability" is still described by using an x with infinite resolution. Directional motion must also be described, but this is traditionally done using changes in x and t . There is no t in this scenario, but there is a shift in density. Thus as argued in (2) there is a density due to built-in ruler gradations, but also a shift in this density showing the direction of motion. This leads to a two dimensional scheme which mathematically may be demonstrated by:

Overall spatial probability = Built-in ruler gradation probability(x) + i shifted gradation probability(x) = $F(x,p) + i G(x,p)$ ((1))

In Part I, we argued $G(x,p)$ must be odd in p because $P(p,x) + P(-p,x) = 2 F(x,p)$ should not contain directional information. Furthermore $F(x,p)$ should be even because it defines the built-in ruler gradation which is the same for p and $-p$.

Spatial Invariance

((1)) is interesting because it is based on the variable x from the external ruler with infinite resolution.

We now consider two approaches to defining $F(x,p)$ and $i G(x,p)$. First we note that both should be periodic in order to give a semblance of invariance in x . Next consider $P(x,p)$ and $P(x,-p)$ i.e. a probability AND its time reversed state together. In such a case there is no motion and so there does not need to be a built-in ruler. Thus as in Part I we suggest:

$$P(p,x)P(-p,x) = \text{constant}$$

$$\text{Thus: } \{F(x,p) - i G(x,p)\} \{F(x,p) + i G(x,p)\} = FF + GG = \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Taking } d/dx \text{ of } ((2)) \text{ yields } F dF/dx = -G dG/dx \quad ((3))$$

An immediate solution would be to have $dF/dx = G$ and $dG/dx = -F$.

So far p has not entered much in the above. We suggest that motion is governed by p and that d/dx is the translational generator which shifts $P(p,x)$.

From information theory, information is $\ln(P(p,x))$. This clearly depends on p and x . Removing x through d/dx should leave p we suggest. We call this assumption ((3)) and discuss it further in the next section.

All of the above then point to $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$.

Constant Motion and Conservation

A particle with constant motion has conserved momentum and energy. Furthermore on average $v = \text{constant} = x/t$ (for motion in the x direction and measurements from a origin and $t=0$). These should be associated with invariance in x and t .

If one suggests: $d/dt f(t) = E$ and $d/dx g(x) = p$ then Et and px as solutions. One may create a Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$ which is both the nonrelativistic/relativistic action as noted above. This begs two questions. Why should E and t and separately p, x be linked and secondly, why should the translation generators for x and t acting on a function of x, t yield conserved quantities?

First we argue that E is associated with time because both are scalars and p vector and r vector may also be associated with (px) x being one component of the dot product.

The second question seems to be directly linked to the notion of Fermat's least time principle. Consider two different paths in two dimensional space. The first hits a flat mirror at x and the second emanates from this same x . There is both conservation of E and (px) . Furthermore, there is invariance in the x direction so one may consider writing:

$d/dx F(x) = (px)$ ((4)) where $F(x)$ is an unknown function.

From Fermat's principle of least time, $F(x)$ is essentially distance(x) or distance(x)/ c or p distance(x) where p is the magnitude of momentum: $\sqrt{p_x p_x + p_y p_y}$ and $d1 = \sqrt{xx + YY}$ and $d2 = \sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + YY}$ where $(x=0, Y)$ and $(x=L, Y)$ are the initial and endpoints.

Thus $F(x) = (px)x + (py)y = p \cdot r = p$ distance because p magnitude is parallel to r . This we argue is the basis for ((3)).

As a result, spatial probability $\exp(ipx)$ chosen above is also connected with conservation of momentum. This is why: $\int dx \exp(-i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \text{constant } \delta(p_1, p_2)$. In other words not only does a particle with constant motion have a built-in clock and ruler, but these ensure conservation of E and (px) if x is an invariant spatial variable.

Conclusion

In conclusion although a particle with constant motion may be described as having on average $x/t = v = \text{constant}$, x and t have infinite resolution and are external. We argue that the particle motion is governed by its own built-in time and spatial gradations. This suggests for space a probability distribution (function of x) creating a spatial gradation (i.e. a set of periodic humps and troughs) which contradicts smooth x/t motion. Thus one cannot follow x in t within this

gradation region so the two variables x, t are independent. This explains $A = \text{classical free particle action} = -Et + px$ and $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt = -E$. If x and t were not independent, such derivatives would make sense it seems.

We further argue that the probability density indicates the direction of motion, but requires two dimensions, each with a function of x . Finally we argue that the built-in time and spatial gradations account for conservation of energy and momentum. These ideas together lead to the form $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ as describing a constantly moving particle.

References

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